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Effects Of Computer Simulation Teaching Strategy On Academic Achievement And Interest Of Upper Basic Social Studies Students In Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates effect of computer simulation teaching strategy on academic achievement of upper basic school students in social studies in Jalingo education zone, Taraba state. The study was guided by two objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted quasi- experimental research design that employed a pre-test, post-test, non- equivalent, control groups. The population of the study was 5698 Social Studies students. The study sampled 202 students in intact classes using multistage sampling technique (experimental group =92, control group =110) from four public upper- basic schools. Computer simulation strategy was used to teach the experimental group while conventional method was used to teach the control group. The instruments used for data collection was Social Studies Achievement Test (SSAT) with reliability coefficients of 0.824 and computed using Kuder Richardson formula. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation for answering the research questions while hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Co-variance (ANCOVA). The study found that Students taught social studies using computer simulation strategy had higher academic achievement mean gain (22.42) than those taught using conventional method (13.18) which was statistically significant $F(df1,201)=115.503$; $P=0.00 < 0.05$. There is no significant effect of computer simulation strategy on academic achievement scores of male and female upper-basic school students in social studies. ($F_{1,91}= 3.364$; $P=0.07 > 0.05$). The study recommended among others that The Curriculum planners should ensure that they incorporate computer simulation strategy into the curriculum of social studies teachers in-training as it helps to promote students' academic achievement in social studies.

Keywords: Computer Simulation Strategy, Conventional Method, Academic Performance, Gender

INTRODUCTION

Social Studies refer to a discipline that is connected with human activities in all ramification of life in order to make them live a fulfilled, worthwhile and acceptable life. As a discipline, it is the study of humans, how and where they live, how they form structures, govern themselves, provide for the needs of

individuals in relation to their environment and how the environment induces human reactions (Odey, 2019). It is the study of human in relation to their community, society and environment; whereby, knowledge, skills, right attitudes and values are inculcated into individuals in order for them to make a positive change in their environment. This area of education integrates knowledge from history, geography, political science, economics, sociology, anthropology, and other social sciences to provide a comprehensive understanding of the world. The goal is to develop informed, responsible, and active citizens who can contribute to the democratic process and address complex social issues.

Upper basic or junior secondary education typically refers to the stage of education that follows primary education and precedes higher secondary or tertiary education. It generally covers early adolescence and includes grades 6 or 7 through 12 to 15 years, depending on the educational system of a particular country. This stage aims to provide students with foundational knowledge and skills in various subjects, preparing them for more advanced studies and helping them to become informed, responsible citizens (UNESCO, 2017). The purpose of basic education is multifaceted, aiming to equip individuals with the essential knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values needed to function effectively in society. It lays the foundation for lifelong learning and personal development, fostering the growth of responsible, informed citizens capable of contributing positively to their communities and the broader world which can be acquired through effective teaching strategies. (UNESCO, 2015).

Teaching strategies are important in implementing the curriculum because they are the means of reaching the predetermine ends (Erionosho, 2013). Teaching methods refer to the general principle, pedagogy and management techniques used for classroom instruction (Kolawole, as cited in Nneka 2019). There are several teaching methods in the field of education. O'banon (2002) categorized teaching method into two approaches; namely the learner centered and the teacher centered approach. The students centered approaches are based on constructivism and includes all the instructional methods that underscores teachers as decision makers and problem solvers but rather as a guide in the teaching process. Student centered methods include discussion, guided inquiry, problem based learning and project. The teachers' role in a student's centered learning environment is at most a facilitator or a guide. The students are in control of their own teaching. Teaching may be independent, collaborative, cooperative and competitive. The utilization and processing of knowledge is more important than the basic contents. While Teachers centered approaches are based on behaviorism and include all the teaching methods that see the teacher as possessor of knowledge. These methods include lecture/expository, demonstration, recitation. A teaching method brings in some type of reality into teaching environment will aggravate the interest of the student thereby ensuring that they have more information about the environment that cannot be acquired from a traditional teaching setting. This can be achieved through the use computer simulation teaching strategy.

Computer simulation have become a popular method of instruction in the last 15 years (Quellmalz, Tims, Silberglitt and Buckley 2012) and this is because of commercially available software that is based on scientific and technological models which replicate actual situations. In a broad sense, simulations are imitations of systems. Simulation is a technique that teaches concepts by imitating or replicating the real objects. Simulation makes significant instructional situation real when well designed. It provides an effective learning environment that enhances the teaching and learning of concepts. The use of simulation helps the teacher to play a more facilitating role that supports learners in a constructive learning process. As a technique for instruction, simulation allows students to deal in a realistic way with matters of vital concern but without dire consequences should they make wrong choices. Simulations enable students to understand complex interactions of physical or social environmental factors. This means technology

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Computer simulation is a teaching technique that reproduces actual events and processes under test conditions (Udoh, 2015). Simulations have been given different meanings by different authors; however, in a broad sense; simulations are imitations of systems. Simulations are computational models of real or hypothesized situations or natural phenomena that allow users to explore the implications of manipulating or modifying parameters within them. It is a teaching strategy involving interaction, computer power point shows which are prepared on a slide. Chen, Nurkhamid, Wang, Yang, Lung and Chang (2013)

opine that Computer simulations provide near-authentic environment, context and situation for task-based learning. As a tool, the computer is used to aid in calculation, graphical displays, animations, simulations and gaming (Okwuduba, Offiah, Madichie, 2018). This shows that learners may learn better when they actively interact with their environment than when they are instructed under conventional method.

Conventional Method is the prevailing method of disseminating knowledge at virtually all levels of education in Nigeria. According to Okonkwo cited in Akpoghol, Ezeudu, Adzape, and Otor (2016) it is the traditional method, the expository method or the talk and chalk as well as conventional method of teaching. The teacher does the bulk of the talking as he presents large body of facts and principles too, in a teacher-centered mode. Conventional Method provides careful, lucid presentation of materials. Participants see the professional mind at work, and it effectively conveys large amount of information in a short space of time. Teachers use mostly the lecture method for imparting information which could end up a creating a passive learning environment in the classroom. Conventional method portrays the instructor as a facilitator of learning activities, a source of information, and a subject matter expert. The instructor should be responsible for all classroom instruction and ensure that all course ideas are comprehended by the pupils (Adanikin and Omojemite, 2021). Teachers use mostly the lecture method for imparting information which could end up creating a passive learning environment in the classroom. The passive learning environment may encourage Gender issues in the learning of concepts.

Gender has been identified as one of the factors influencing student's academic performance at secondary school level (Fagbemi, Gambari, Oyedum, and Gbodi, 2011). This is the reason why gender issue has received the attentions of many researchers across disciplines and at different levels of education (including the Upper Basic Education level). Gender disparity in academic performance in Studies prevails in schools where subject are offered (Essien, 2015). In Nigeria, some works have been carried out to study gender difference in achievement in some specific fields and that, gender achievement has not received much attention in this part of the country that has a long history of poor female achievement in formal education generally (Yusuf and Yakub, 2013). Therefore, computer simulation has been found to equalize the status and respect for all group members, regardless of gender which either give students a positive interest or negative interest in the course of learning.

Academic performance in any given subject especially social studies is one of the major parameters used in assessing and determining the progress of students in an academic programme. It is considered to be the centre around which the education system revolves and determines the success or failure of any academic institution (Amalu & Nanjwan, 2019). Student academic performance measures the amount of academic content a student learns in a determined amount of time. Academic achievement can also be used as indices for determining students' ability to effectively undertake another task (Jimoh, Idris & Olatunji, 2016). The academic performance involves factors such as the intellectual level, personality, motivation, skills, interests, study habits, self-esteem or the teacher student relationship. When a gap between the academic performance and the student's expected performance occurs, it refers to a diverging performance. The average performance of students as observed by the researcher among social studies students in recent times has been attributed partly to teachers not using the appropriate teaching strategies. The BECE examination gave the percentage failure of students as follows: 2019 (28%), 2020 (31%), 2021 (22%), 2022 (31%), 2023 (23%) in Taraba state Nigeria. This gives an average percentage failure rate of 27% in social studies with most students passing at average from (2019-2023). It is against this background that the researcher intends to study the effect of computer simulation teaching strategy on upper basic school students' academic achievement in Social Studies in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba state.

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The Average performance among students has attracted the attention of educationists and researchers as a major problem to development in Nigeria. The Nigerian government at various levels, individuals and cooperate bodies attached great importance to the teaching and learning of social science education courses, yet these objectives as observed have not been fully achieved over the years due to problems bordering among students. This concerns cut across all school subjects at all levels of education system. This however, has negatively affected many upper basic Schools leavers the opportunity of performing

better when offered admission into the senior secondary school level and institution of higher learning which constitutes the problem of the study. This average performance if not checked, Taraba state will continue to lag behind in filling her quota in social sciences related courses in tertiary institution and in jobs opportunities. As important as teaching and learning is, educators have been lamenting over students' performance of students in the subject. The problems of students' performance have been attributed partly to teachers not using the appropriate teaching methodologies. In view of this ailing problem, the search for a modern and appropriate alternative to teaching becomes necessary. Hence, it is on this basis that the study intends to investigate the effects of computer simulation teaching strategy on academic achievement and social studies students in Jalingo education zone, Taraba state.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the mean academic performance scores of students taught social studies with computer simulation teaching strategy and those with conventional method in Jalingo education zone, Taraba State?
2. What are the mean academic performance scores of students taught Social Studies using computer simulation teaching strategy based on gender in Jalingo education zone, Taraba State?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught social studies with Computer simulation teaching strategy and those with conventional method in Jalingo education zone, Taraba State.

HO₂: There is no significant difference in mean academic performance scores of students taught Social Studies using computer simulation teaching strategy based on gender in Jalingo education zone, Taraba State

Theoretical Framework

Cognitive Field Theory (David Paul Ausubel theory of Meaningful Learning, (1963)

Similarly the computer simulation strategy employs the fundamental ideals of the cognitive field theory e.g. Ausubel theory of learning .These theorists view learning as an interaction between the cognitive structure and the new or incoming information and this interaction results in meaningful learning. The simulation environment, affords the learner ample opportunity for this interaction. Simulation-game teaching strategy ensures that the material to be learned is conceptually clear and presented with language and examples that are related to the learners' prior knowledge. The main concept to be learned is also broken down into smaller units and subordinate concepts and there after arranged hierarchically from simple to the complex as the game progresses. Hierarchical arrangement of the concepts is one of the fundamental ideals of the cognitive theorists.

The computer simulation teaching strategy enables the learner to communicate in an in-depth understanding of a problem or issue rather than memorize sets of isolated facts and this result in achievements that have relevance beyond school (Akinsola and Animashun, 2007). Teaching and learning Social Studies should go beyond classroom activity and involve the learners' environment and practices. This approach which is embedded in simulation-game strategy will make learning meaningful for the learner while effectively preparing them for work place and life after schooling.

The computer simulation strategy by its nature involves learning by doing or behaving, that is doing something active, that one can control. The activity and problem based nature of the strategy helps the learner to be inquisitive, explorative and initiative in the process of learning as posited by the cognitive field theorists. The nature of the learners' mental interaction with the subject matter to be learned during the

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The fundamental ideas in this theory can also be employed in computer simulation. These meta-cognitive teaching tools help to foster creativity and co-operation between students and teachers. There is at this time a vigorous search for strategies that can be used to deliver effectively and efficiently good quality

chemical education. Computer simulation as reported in literature may be potent in enhancing knowledge and skill acquisition. The relevance of Ausubel's theory of meaningful learning to this study lies in the fact that this study used computer simulation teaching strategy to measure Social Studies students' academic achievement in the teaching of Social Studies. This theory laid more emphasis on the active involvement of learners in the learning process through more innovative strategy which is focus of computer simulation teaching strategy. The theory opines that if a child is given the opportunity to explore or construct knowledge by himself, he will be motivated to learn more of social studies. If this theory is effectively implemented by teachers, teaching of art subjects must begin with new learning or knowledge in a sequential manner. Social Studies teachers must not present new materials during teaching unless the learner is ready. Ausubel supported the use of expository method in teaching of social studies as a subjects, the method can lead to high level of understanding and generality as against the use of lecture method and contents in the social studies curriculum.

Conceptual Framework

Computer Simulation

Computer simulation as a concept could be referred to a tool that can be manipulated in order to effect some changes in a model before invoking a particular change in the real world. According to Guy and Lownes-Jackson (2015), computer simulations have been used to support variations of cognitive learning styles, to facilitate higher order thinking and problem-solving skills and to augment differential, collaborative and mastery learning. Perhaps, it was on this note that Williams (2016) noted that visual classroom is a digital technology driven classroom that support self-directed and regulated learning. This means that social studies teachers and regulated learning. This means that social studies teachers should be well rooted in the use of technological strategy alongside the conventional method of effective teaching and learning process to be actualized.

The advancement of civilization is making learning even much easier through utilization of electronic devices. Amongst these are the computers and its accessories (the Compact Disc (CDs) and the programme software packages), the internet, World Wide Web (www), electronic mail and the satellite (Udo and Etiubon, 2011). A computer simulation strategy is an attempt to model a real-life or hypothetical situation on a computer so that it can be studied to see how the system works. According to Gatto (2013), interactive simulation computer power point show, it is a computer simulations programs that allow the user to interact with a computer representation of scientific model of natural or physical world. The computer has many functions, one of which is to assist in classroom instruction. It is possible to use computer to deliver instruction in the classroom either partially or totally. Enohuan (2015) added that for effective instructional processes, teaching should be made with visual aids such as computer

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This is the oldest teaching method applied in educational institutions. This teaching method is one way channel of communication of information. Conventional teaching strategy is a teaching without using any activity-based or instructional material by the teacher. It is mainly authoritarian in nature whereby teaching– learning is not based on hands-on activities. In this teaching strategy, teachers often teach the way they were taught sometimes using the same notebooks they used as students (Udoh, 2015). Students' involvement in this teaching method is just to listen and sometimes pen down some notes if necessary during the lecture, combine the information and organized it. According to (Radhika, 2020) this strategy lays more emphasis on teacher's knowledge on the topic than that of the students. In the pure lecture mode, the teacher dominates the class teaching. The teacher tells the students what he wants them to know and the students listen, copy notes and memorize it. Students are rarely involved actively in this teaching method. The advantages of this method include: It allows for adequate coverage of the course content in a short time, Economy of time and materials ,it fosters good teacher student relationship, Students can collect valid notes from the teacher, student listening skills developed, and logical arrangement of the material in order to present it orally. The disadvantages of Conventional method: Teacher delivers the same lecture to both students without recognizing the individual differences, learning

is an active process thus students should be encourage to actively participate in the class room instead of just listening the teacher ,it favors high achievers and gifted children, lacks active participation of students, does not cater for individual differences , does not take into consideration the students initiative, Abstract presentation of ideas. Lecture teaching method (LTM) is a teacher-centered method which makes the learner a passive recipient of information. There is little or no students' active participation, students are merely required to listen and understand the information being given and that is why it is also called teacher centered (Eze, Ezenwafor & Obidile, 2018).

Academic Achievement

Academic achievement is the knowledge gained which is assessed by marks by a teacher and/or educational goals set by students and teachers to be achieved over a specific period of time (Goshi, 2020). It is considered to be the centre around which the education system revolves and determines the success or failure of any academic institution (Amalu and Ndifon, 2017). MeenuDev (2016) stated that, academic achievement of students is not only a pointer to the effectiveness or otherwise of schools but a major determinant of the future of youths in particular and the nation in general. Academic achievement means how much knowledge the individual has acquired from the school (Bashir & Mattoo, 2012). Nkemakolam in Ozioko (2014) noted that achievement test is a measure of the level of accomplishment in a specified programme of instruction undertaken by a student in the recent past and can be classified on the basis of purpose, reference point, quality, content, scoring and equipment used.

Concept of Gender

Gender refers to social differentiation or cultural distinction between male and female and the attribution of certain roles on the basis of differentiation (Abe, Egbon, and Aduloju, 2013). .Gender refers to one's status of either being a male or female and it has become a very important issue among researchers. It is an important factor in the learning process and in educational setting which has been focused upon because of their significance in the development of any nation (Udoh & Eton, 2018). Gender refers to the biological and physiological reality of being male or female (Igbo, Onu and Obiyo, 2015). Also, Igbo et al, described gender as a behavior pattern and attitude perceived as a masculine and feminine within a culture. Additionally, it is a social and cultural construct which distinguishes the difference in the attributes of men and women, boys and girls and accordingly refers to the roles of men and women (Santrock, 2010). Several Studies have been carried out on effect of gender on academic performance and interest which has led to a number of conflicting conclusions. Some study found gender as a relevant factor in students' interest and academic performance, while others found no difference between the sexes in interest and academic performance. Many reasons have been given as explanations to male students' superiority over their female counterparts in the social science subjects. For instance, the noted superiority could be attributed to sex stereotypes which involve male and female students relevant to the roles they are exposed to fill in the society (Rampacher and Peterson, 2013). In this study students gender comprises of male and female upper basic two Social Studies students that will be taught using computer simulation strategy and conventional teaching method

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The study adopted quasi- experimental research design that employed a pre-test, post-test, non-equivalent, control groups. The population of the study was 5698 Social Studies students. The study sampled 202 students in intact classes using multistage sampling technique (experimental group =92, control group =110) from four public upper- basic schools. Computer simulation strategy was used to teach the experimental group while conventional method was used to teach the control group. The instruments used for data collection was Social Studies Achievement Test (SSAT). The Social Studies Achievement Test (SSAT) was subjected to face and content validation by three experts, one expert from measurements and evaluation, one expert from social science education and one expert from curriculum and instruction. The instrument was trial tested on 40 social studies students outside the study area and yielded a reliability coefficients of 0.824 computed using Kuder Richardson formula. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation for answering the research questions while hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Co-variance (ANCOVA).

RESULTS

Research question 1: *What are the mean academic performance scores of students taught social studies with computer simulation teaching strategy and those with conventional method in Jalingo education zone, Taraba State?*

Table 1: Mean Academic Achievement Scores of Students Taught Social Studies with Computer Simulation Teaching Strategy and those with Conventional Method

Teaching Method	N	Pre-test		Post test		Mean Gain
		Mean	Std	Mean	Std	
Computer Simulation	92	12.49	2.64	34.91	4.27	22.42
Conventional method	110	14.45	3.02	27.63	4.85	13.18
Mean Difference		1.96		7.28		9.37

Results on table 2 shows the mean pretest and posttest achievement scores in social studies for students taught with computer simulation strategy and those taught with conventional method. The post test means score of students taught using computer simulation method is 34.91 with standard deviation of 4.27 while that of those taught using conventional method is 27.63 with standard deviation of 4.85. The difference between the pre-test and post test mean scores of computer simulation is 22.42 while that of the conventional method is 13.18. The pre-test and post test means score differences for the two groups shows that the computer simulation group is higher. There is also a difference of 9.37 between the post test mean scores of the two group in favour of the computer simulation group. This suggest that students taught using computer simulation teaching strategies had higher mean than their counter part using conventional method.

Research question 2: *What are the mean academic performance scores of students taught Social Studies using computer simulation teaching strategy based on gender in Jalingo education zone, Taraba State?*

Table 2: Mean Academic Achievement Scores of Students Taught Social Studies using Computer Simulation Teaching Strategy Based on Gender

Computer Simulation	N	Pre-test		Post test		Mean Gain
		Mean	Std	Mean	Std	
Male	58	13.24	2.73	35.86	4.09	22.62
Female	34	11.23	1.91	33.65	4.38	22.42
Mean Difference		2.01		1.51		0.2

Table 2 reveals the mean pretest and posttest scores of male and female students when taught social studies using computer simulation strategy. The male students pretest and posttest mean scores are 13.24 (Std 2.73) and 35.56 (Std 4.09) which yielded a mean gain of 22.62 while the females' students pretest and posttest mean scores are 11.23 (Std 1.91) and 33.65 (Std 4.38) which yielded a mean gain of 22.42. The mean gain difference between the male and female student is 0.2. This implies that the male student had higher mean gain than the female students when taught social studies using computer simulation strategy.

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught social studies with Computer simulation teaching strategy and those with conventional method in Jalingo education zone

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Table: 3 Summary of ANCOVA of Significant Difference in the Mean Achievement Scores Of Students Taught Social Studies with Computer Simulation Teaching Strategy and those with Conventional Method.

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects
Dependent Variable: POSTTEST

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	2663.769a	2	1331.884	62.947	.000	.387
Intercept	8025.249	1	8025.249	379.284	.000	.656
PRETEST	4.390	1	4.390	.207	.649	.001
TEACHING_STRATEGY	2443.933	1	2443.933	115.503	.000*	.367
Error	4210.632	199	21.159			
Total	200315.000	202				
Corrected Total	6874.401	201				

a. R Squared = .387 (Adjusted R Squared = .381)

Table 3 presents the two-way ANCOVA results on effect of computer simulation strategy and conventional method on students' academic performance in social studies. The result of the analysis reveals that there is significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of social studies students when taught using computer simulation strategy and those taught with conventional method $F(1, 201) = 115.503$, $P < 0.05$. Since the computed P-value (0.00) is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected and concluded that there is significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of social studies students when taught using computer simulation strategy and those taught with conventional method in favour of those taught with computer simulation strategy. More so, the partial Eta-squared (0.367) was reported which indicates that large effect size (37%).

HO₂: There is no significant difference in mean academic performance scores of students taught Social Studies using computer simulation teaching strategy based on gender in Jalingo education zone, Taraba State

Table 4: Summary of ANCOVA of the Mean academic achievement of students Taught Social Studies using Computer Simulation Teaching Strategy based on Gender
Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: POSTTEST_COMPUTER

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	86.229a	2	43.115	2.449	.092	.052
Intercept	3968.101	1	3968.101	225.363	.000	.717
PRETEST_COMPUTER	3.763	1	3.763	.214	.645	.002
GENDER	59.240	1	59.240	3.364	.070*	.036
Error	1567.075	89	17.608			
Total	113794.000	92				
Corrected Total	1653.304	91				

a. R Squared = .052 (Adjusted R Squared = .031)

Table 4 presents the ANCOVA results on effect of computer simulation strategy on students' academic achievement in social studies based on gender. The result of the analysis reveals that there is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of social studies students when taught using computer simulation strategy based on gender $F(1, 91) = 3.364$, $P > 0.05$. Since the computed P-value (0.07) is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is accepted and concluded that there is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of social studies students when taught using computer simulation strategy and those taught with conventional method based on gender.

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DISCUSSION

The result reveals that students taught social studies using computer strategy had higher mean academic achievement scores than those taught using conventional method. This finding was also confirmed by ANCOVA for significant difference which showed that there is significant difference between the academic achievement scores of students taught social studies with computer simulation strategy. The

finding is in line with that of Njoku (2015), Okwudubam, Offiah and Medichic (2018), Ayuba (2017), Ojo (2020) This may be because computer simulation strategy uses model in a real-life or hypothetical situation on a computer so that it can be studied to see how the system works. These programs can be used as demonstration by the teachers, or they can be used directly by students to explore various systems and manipulate variables which enhance students' achievement.

The study indicates that the male students had higher mean gain academic performance scores than females' students when taught social studies using computer simulation strategy. There is no significant effect of computer simulation strategy on academic achievement scores of male and female upper-basic school students in social studies. This finding agree with Egara, Eseadi and Nzeadibe (2022), Lasisi, Oti, Arowolo and Ojoko (2021), Alake and Olojo (2020), Akhigbe and Ogufere (2019) but the findings contradict that of Cezar (2024), Ibitomi, Oloyede and Olorundare (2022), Ibezim and Azogwa (2020) whose findings shows a significant difference in gender achievement of students when exposed to computer simulation strategy.

CONCLUSION

The study investigate the effect of computer simulation teaching strategy on academic achievement of upper basic social studies students in Jalingo education zone, Taraba state Nigeria. Specifically, the study has shown that an effective teaching method that is learner centered and innovative such as computer simulation strategy enhances students' academic performance of upper- basic social studies students. Lastly, the current study has shown that the male students had higher mean academic performance scores than females' students when taught social studies using computer simulation strategy. However, it did not show a significant difference in the academic performance of male and female students taught social studies using computer simulation strategy which implies that computer simulation strategy is gender friendly.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The study therefore recommend based on the finding of this study that, teachers should integrate innovative simulation into their instructional modes especially when teaching abstract concepts.
2. Equal attention should be given to male and female students in developing their performance in social studies.

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